

Constitution of 2,6-Dimethoxyquinone-acetone

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The addition product of 2,6-dimethoxyquinone and acetone is found to give phloroglucinol derivatives by degradation. The final reduction and methylation product is propyl¹ phloroglucinol trimethyl ether which has been independently synthesised for comparison. These reactions prove that the addition has taken place in the 1-position of the quinone.

In an earlier publication¹, Aghoramurthy, Rao, and Seshadri described a new water-soluble and sweet compound obtained from 2,6-dimethoxyquinone and acetone under the influence of anhydrous potassium carbonate. They showed that this compound was derived from one molecule of each of the components, had an alcoholic group, and gave iodoform reaction. The formula (I) was suggested for the compound since the carbonyl group in the 1-position of the quinone could be considered to be unreactive due to steric hindrance. More recently, unaware of the earlier report, Magnusson^{2,3} has been studying the action of quinones (mainly *o*-quinones) with acetone in presence of aluminium oxide and in a preliminary note² has suggested the alternative structure (II) for the dimethoxyquinone-acetone adduct from considerations of reactivity of the carbonyl groups. The experimental results reported herein agree with this structure. In the reaction therefore steric effects are unimportant and deactivation of the C=O group in the 4-position by electromeric polarisation from the methoxyl groups is the main factor (III).

The addition product is most conveniently prepared by the potassium carbonate method; the alumina method seems to furnish a very poor yield. The compound (II) has been tested for antibiotic property and is found to be active (unpublished work). Its water-solubility can be considered an added advantage, as most of the quinones having antibiotic properties suffer from poor solubility.

The reduction of the tertiary hydroxyl group of similar compounds has already been done using a variety of reagents: titanium trichloride, sodium dithionite, stannous chloride⁴,

1. *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1953, 37A, 798.
2. *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1958, 12, 791.
3. *Ibid.*, 1960, 14, 1643.
4. Ried *et al.*, *Angew. Chem.*, 1958, 70, 270.

phenylhydrazine⁵, and zinc dust and acetic acid^{6,3}. The last seems to be most convenient; the quinone-acetone adduct undergoes reduction by this method readily to form a dimethoxymonohydroxyphenylacetone (IV). This compound is soluble in alkali and insoluble in water; it can be methylated and it gives characteristic reactions and spectrum for a carbonyl group. These indicate that it is a phenol with a ketonic side chain. Its methyl ether (V) has been subjected to the Clemmensen reduction and the product is found to be identical with propyl⁹ phloroglucinol trimethyl ether, obtained independently from phloropropiophenone dimethyl ether by reduction followed by methylation. Further, it is found that the aromatic derivatives of the adduct give colours ranging from purple to blue with vanillin and hydrochloric acid in ethanolic solution, a test generally given by the phloroglucinol system^{7,8}. The above series of transformations establishes structure (II) for the adduct. The alternative structure (I) would have led to a pyrogallol derivative. These transformations are shown below:

The Clemmensen reduction of the trimethoxyphenylacetone was difficult and afforded a poor yield of the product. The difficulty in this reduction can be due to the steric hindrance offered by the *ortho*-methoxyls. It may be mentioned here that 2, 4, 6-trimethoxybenzaldehyde, in which similar substitution exists, is reported to be unreducible under similar conditions. The *ortho*-hydroxyketone (VII) can, however, be easily reduced.

The infrared spectra of the addition compound and the various transformation products are in full agreement with the above formulas. (i) The quinone-acetone adduct (II) shows a strong absorption at 3400 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the alcoholic hydroxyl group.

5. Clark, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 463.

6. Ingold, *ibid.*, 1926, 3080.

7. Kursanov, *Biokhimiya*, 1941, 6, 253.

8. Hillis and Carle, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1960, 13, 390.

9. Mauthner, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1931, 129, 281.

The tertiary nature of the hydroxyl is indicated by another absorption at 1370 cm^{-1} . A strong peak at 1720 cm^{-1} corresponds to the keto group in the side chain. The quinone carbonyl absorbs at 1667 cm^{-1} . The two frequencies at 1616 cm^{-1} and 1595 cm^{-1} can be attributed to the double bonds of the quinonoid system in the adduct. (ii) The reduction product (IV) shows a medium absorption at 3225 cm^{-1} , indicative of a phenolic hydroxyl. The ketonic absorption of this compound is lower (1695 cm^{-1}) owing to possible intermolecular hydrogen-bond formation (IX). The conjugated carbonyl band (1667 cm^{-1}) and the tertiary alcoholic absorption (1370 cm^{-1}) of (II) have disappeared in this compound. A medium absorption at 1600 cm^{-1} shows its aromatic nature. (iii) The methyl ether (V) has a normal aliphatic carbonyl absorption (1720 cm^{-1}) and it shows aromatic absorption at 1613 cm^{-1} . (iv) The Clemmensen reduction product (VI) is devoid of the carbonyl absorption and shows aromatic absorption at 1613 cm^{-1} (nujol medium).

UV spectrum of the quinone-acetone adduct (II) in methanol solution has two maxima at wave lengths $244\text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon, 4.21$) and $294\text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon, 3.64$).

EXPERIMENTAL

Melting points are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were taken on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord using KBr disc method unless otherwise mentioned and the UV spectrum on a Hilger Spectrophotometer. Light petroleum used had boiling range of $40\text{-}60^\circ$.

The adduct used in the following reactions was prepared by the potassium carbonate method¹. After completely evaporating the acetone, extraction of the crude product with hot benzene was found to be more convenient for its purification. The hot benzene extract deposited colorless crystals of the adduct on cooling. Crystallisation from ethyl acetate-light petroleum also gave satisfactory results.

Reduction of the Adduct to 2,6-Dimethoxy-4-hydroxyphenylacetone (IV)

An ice-cold solution of the adduct (6 g.) in glacial acetic acid (120 ml) was treated with zinc dust (60 g.). The mixture was shaken vigorously for 2 hrs. with occasional cooling. The excess of zinc was filtered and washed with acetic acid. The combined filtrate and washings were distilled under reduced pressure to remove most of the acetic acid. The residue was diluted with water (100 ml) and the turbid mixture was left in a refrigerator, when a pale brown solid separated. It was filtered, dried, and crystallised from ethyl acetate-light petroleum giving colorless prisms (4 g.), m.p. 94° . It is practically insoluble in aqueous

10. Cantor *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1245.

sodium carbonate, but dissolves readily in aqueous sodium hydroxide and gave no ferric reaction. It gave a violet solution with H_2SO_4 (conc.), a purple colour with vanillin and HCl, and a positive iodoform reaction. (Found: C, 62.5; H, 7.0. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{14}O_4$: C, 62.9; H, 6.7%). 2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of the ketone was obtained as silky needles from ethanol, m.p. 209°. (Found: C, 52.2; H, 5.1. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{18}O_7N_4$: C, 52.3; H, 4.7%).

2,4,6-Trimethoxyphenylacetone (V)

A solution of the ketone(IV) (0.5 g.) in dry acetone (20 ml) was refluxed for 7 hrs. with anhydrous potassium carbonate (2 g.) and dimethyl sulphate (0.5 ml). The mixture was filtered and the inorganic residue was washed with hot acetone. The combined filtrate and washings were distilled to remove acetone. The residue was treated with aqueous sodium hydroxide (20%, 50 ml), the alkaline mixture extracted with chloroform, the extract dried (sodium sulphate), the solvent distilled, and the residue crystallised from chloroform-light petroleum, yielding colorless stout prisms (0.42 g.), m.p. 88°. With vanillin and HCl it gave a bluish violet colour which became indigo-blue on standing and with H_2SO_4 , a light brown colour. (Found: C, 64.7; H, 7.7. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{16}O_4$: C, 64.3; H, 7.2%).

2,4,6-Trimethoxy-1-propyl¹⁰ benzene (VI)

(i) *By Clemmensen Reduction of the Trimethoxy Ketone (V)*.—The methyl ether (V) (0.45 g.) in ethanol (10 ml) was added to a mixture of amalgamated zinc (from 2.5 g. zinc powder), distilled water (2.0 ml), and HCl (conc., 2.5 ml) and refluxed for 10 hrs. More HCl (1 ml) was added every 2 hrs. during refluxing. The unchanged amalgam was filtered and the filtrate steam-distilled until the distillate was coming clear. Long colorless needles separated from the turbid distillate on keeping in a refrigerator for 3 days. These were filtered and dried (0.03 g.), m.p. 46-47°, undepressed by an authentic sample prepared by the following method; colour reactions were also similar. When extracted and worked up as described earlier, the non-volatile portion gave 0.25 g. of the unreduced ketone.

In another experiment, the methyl ether (V) (0.2 g.) in ethanol (10 ml) was added to amalgamated zinc (from 3 g. of zinc dust), distilled water (2 ml), and HCl (2.5 ml) and refluxed. At the end of 5 hrs., the same quantities of zinc amalgam, water, and acid were added and refluxing was continued for another 5 hrs. This was repeated twice so that 12 g. of zinc was used up and refluxing was done for 20 hrs. The product was worked up as given earlier; its yield was 55 mg. The recovered ketone weighed 90 mg.

(ii) *By Synthesis: (a) 2-Hydroxy-4,6-dimethoxypropionophenone¹⁰*.—Anhydrous aluminium chloride in absolute ether (400 ml) was mixed in the cold with phloroglucinol trimethyl ether (6g.) and an ethereal solution of propionyl chloride (2.9 g. in 10 ml ether). The mixture was kept in a refrigerator for 40 hrs. The ether was decanted and the oily residue washed with dry ether. The aluminium chloride complex was decomposed by addition of crushed ice and HCl. The mixture was then heated on a water bath for 30 mins. The solid separating on cooling was filtered, dried, and crystallised from ethanol giving colorless plates (4.8 g.), m. p. 110-111°; Canter *et al.*¹⁰ reported m.p. 111° for the sample prepared by the Hoesch reaction using phloroglucinol dimethyl ether and propionitrile. It gave a wine-red colour with ferric chloride and a deep blue colour with HNO_3 (conc.).

(b) *Reduction and Methylation*.—The above ketone (4.8 g.) was subjected to the Clemmensen reduction by refluxing for 6 hrs. with amalgamated zinc (from 25 g. zinc dust), distilled water (20 ml), HCl (conc., 40 ml), and ethanol (80 ml.). After evaporating the ethanol, the product was ether-extracted, the extract dried (sodium sulphate), and the solvent distilled. The semisolid residue left behind (crude, 4.5 g.) contained some unchanged ketone since it gave a slight brown colour with ferric chloride. It was difficult to purify and was used as such in the next step where removal of the unreduced ketone was easy.

The crude product (4.4 g.) from the previous reaction was boiled for 6 hrs. with acetone (100 ml), dimethyl sulphate (2.6 ml), and anhydrous potassium carbonate (15 g.). After filtration and evaporation of the filtrate, the product was treated with 10% NaOH solution (50 ml) and steam-distilled. On keeping in a refrigerator, the milky steam distillate deposited clusters of colorless needles which were filtered and recrystallised from dilute ethanol, yield 3g., m. p. 47°. It did not give any colour with ferric chloride or with nitric acid. With vanillin and HCl, it gave a blood-red colour changing to violet. (Found: C, 68.5; H, 8.9. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{18}O_3$: C, 68.5; H, 8.6%).

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